

DAMAGE-TYPE IDENTIFICATION IN A CFRP CROSS-PLY LAMINATE FROM ACOUSTIC EMISSION SIGNALS DETECTED BY A FIBER-OPTIC SENSOR IN A NEW REMOTE CONFIGURATION

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ABSTRACT

Recently, the authors have developed a highly sensitive fiber-optic ultrasonic sensing system using a phase-shifted fiber Bragg grating (PSFBG). The sophisticated PSFBG sensing system enabled us to detect acoustic emission (AE) waves generated by micro-damages in composite materials. This research attempted to establish a reliable method for damage types identification in CFRP laminates by analysing the detected AE signals. To enhance the performance of the method for practical AE detections during material tests, first of all, we proposed a new remote measurement configuration. Instead of a direct attachment, in the configuration, a lead optical fiber was mounted onto the material sample and used as a waveguide to propagate AEs from composite to the PSFBG. Because the PSFBG sensor was put away from the adhesive point, it was insensitive to the static strain applied to the material. That resulted in a stable AE measurement during material tests, such as tensile tests. Interestingly, experiments figured out that the remotely located PSFBG sensor still demonstrated accurate remote sensing for AE signal propagating through the adhesive point. Taking advantage of the great sensing characteristics, we analysed AE signals on the basis of a Lamb wave theory to quantitatively identify the damage types in the CFRP laminates. As a result, the analysis showed different characteristics of Lamb wave modes included in three types of AEs caused by a transverse crack, delamination and fiber breakage. The analysis also revealed that the peak frequencies in the AE signals had a correlation with the modes. Additionally, the ratios of the amplitudes of the S_0 mode to the A_0 mode and the peak frequencies quantitatively evaluated the mode characteristics in the AE signals. Simultaneously using the two physical parameters, we identified the three types of damage among the AE signals detected in a three-point bending test. Hence, the proposed identification method with the PS-FBG sensor has great physical reliability for evaluating damage in composite laminates.

1 INTRODUCTION

Acoustic emission (AE) detection is a non-destructive testing (NDT) method for evaluating damage processes in structural composites. Recently, fiber-optic Bragg gratings (FBGs) have been applied to AE detection [1-3]. Because of their good flexibility and durability, immunity to electro-magnetic interference (EMI), and ability to be embedded in composites, FBGs have potential for extending the application of AE detection to the structural health monitoring of composites [4, 5].

However, since common FBG-based AE sensors have low sensitivities and limited frequency bandwidths, quantitative analysis on the detected AE signals were difficult. To develop the sensor for strong performance for AE detection, Wu and Okabe [6] used a special type of FBG, phase-shifted FBG (PS-FBG) sensor. Because of its high sensitivity and broad frequency bandwidth, that sensor was able to detect AE signals with small energy in CFRP laminates [7-9].

In addition, PSFBG sensors have the advantage of adding high physical reliability to the AE detection results because the Bragg wavelength shift of FBGs is proportional to the change in the axial strain. By demodulating the shift at a high frequency measurement [10], the dynamic strain caused by AE waves could be correctly detected using an FBG sensor. Since AE waves propagate as a Lamb

wave in the plate-shaped structure [11, 12], analyzing the detected AE waveforms on the basis of the elastic wave theory has great potential to identify damage types.

This research attempted to establish a physically reliable method to identify damage types in CFRP laminates through analysing the AE signals detected by the PS-FBG sensor. F. Yu et al. [9] extracted amplitude ratios of the S_0 and A_0 modes from AE signals to quantitatively evaluate the occurrence of transverse cracks and delaminations in CFRP laminates. However, because only one parameter was used, the method was not sufficient to identify damage among all the AE events.

The aim of the present paper was to improve the identification method by using an additional parameter with good physical reliability. As an important characteristic in wave propagation, the peak frequency of AE attracted our attention. This was because the broad bandwidth [6] allows a PS-FBG sensor to examine AEs with different peak frequencies. Utilizing the peak frequency and the amplitude ratio simultaneously could improve the quantitative identification method involving the PS-FBG sensor.

To enhance performance of the PSFBG sensor for practical AE detection, first of all, this research proposed a special detection configuration shown in Figure 1 (a). In this configuration, the optical fiber without the PS-FBG was glued onto the structural plate. The segment of optical fiber between the adhesive and the PS-FBG was used as the AE propagation waveguide. The PS-FBG sensor detected the propagating dynamic strain in the waveguide. In the present paper, we named this special detection configuration a new adhesive method for remote AE measurement (ADRM).

The ADRM-based AE detection configuration was different from typical AE and ultrasonic detection methods in which sensors were glued onto surface of materials or structures. However, in addition to the dynamic strain caused by ultrasonic wave, the direct attachment also lead static strain applied to the structures to shifting spectrums of FBG and PSFBG sensors. Thus the typical adhesive method disturbs the AE measurement using the PSFBG sensor during material tests, such as tensile tests. Conversely, through putting the PSFBG sensor away from the adhesive point, the ADRM configuration could protect the sensor from the static strain and achieve a stable AE detection.

As mentioned above, the damage identification method proposed in the present paper depends on correct responses to the S_0 mode and A_0 mode included in AE. Hence, in the section 2, we studied sensing characteristics of the PS-FBG sensor in the ADRM configuration in order to verify that the special method could detect the accurate modes. Then, In Section 3, AE detection using the ADRM configuration clarified the characteristics of Lamb wave modes in the AE signals caused by transverse cracks, delaminations and fiber breaks in CFRP laminates. To evaluate the mode characteristics quantitatively, the amplitude ratio and the peak frequency were extracted from the AE signals. On the basis of these two parameters, we classified AE signals that had been detected using the PS-FBG sensor to identify the specified three types of damage among a number of detected events during a three-point bending test.

2 ADHESIVE METHOD FOR REMOTE AE MEASUREMENT

In the ADRM configuration, waves propagate through the waveguide of the optical fiber from the adhesive point to the PS-FBG. The wave propagation in the optical fiber possibly influences the detection of the Lamb wave modes. Hence, an experiment shown in Figure 1 was conducted in order to investigate the wave propagation, and verify that the PS-FBG sensor in the ADRM configuration is still able to detect Lamb wave modes correctly.

The experiment was carried out on an aluminum plate (length: 100 cm; thickness: 0.3 cm; width: 100 cm) large enough to prevent detection of waves reflected at the edges of the plate. A piezoactuator-type macrofiber composite (MFC) (M-8714-P2, Smart Material Corporation) was glued on the aluminum plate to excite the aluminum plate at ultrasonic frequencies. The ultrasonic waves were detected via the PS-FBG sensor with polyimide coating (Fujikura Corporation) connected to the balanced sensing system [6]. The optical fiber was glued onto the aluminum plate using commercial Cyanoacrylate adhesives with a length of 5 mm. Figure 1(a) illustrates the position of the adhesive point and the PS-FBG sensor in the ADRM configuration. The notation ADRM ($D_{\text{Sensor}}-D_{\text{Adhesive}}$) is used to indicate the different distance conditions between the adhesive point and the PS-FBG sensor, where D_{Adhesive} (cm) indicates the distance between the MFC and the adhesive, and D_{Sensor} (cm)

indicates the distance from the MFC to the PS-FBG. In Figure 1(b), the notation AD (D_{Sensor}) describes the normal adhesive method, where the PS-FBG sensor was directly glued on the plate surface at the position D_{Sensor} (cm) away from the actuator.

Figure 1: Experimental setup: (a) adhesive method for remote measurement (ADRM) and (b) normal adhesive method (AD).

Figure 2: Response to the input signal of a three-cycle sinusoidal wave with Hamming windows in (a) AD(40), (b) AD(20), (c) ADRM(40-20), and (d) ADRM(60-20). Continuous wavelet transform (CWT) results corresponding to the temporal waveforms in (e) AD(40), (f) AD (20), (g) ADRM(40-20), and (h) ADRM(60-20).

The MFC was used to generate a three-cycle sinusoidal wave excitation with a hamming window. In the ADRM configurations, the adhesive point was located 20 cm away from the MFC, and the sensor position was located 40 and 60 cm away from the MFC, resulting in ADRM(40-20) and ADRM(60-20) configurations, respectively. In addition, normal adhesive methods with distances of 20 and 40 cm between the MFC and PS-FBG, respectively, were also used as references. They resulted in AD(20) and AD(40) configurations, respectively.

Figure 2 shows the responses to an input signal with a central frequency of 300 kHz. Temporal waveforms corresponding to the four adhesive conditions are shown in Figures 2(a) to 2(d). Time 0 indicates the beginning time of the input signal. The continuous wavelet transform (CWT) results corresponding to the respective waveforms [13] are shown in Figures 2(e) to 2(h). On the basis of the theoretical dispersive curve of the arrival time against the frequency, the S_0 mode and the A_0 mode were separated as shown in Figures 2(a) and 2(b). Then, referring to the result in AD(20), it was observed that the wave components having the same characteristics as that of the S_0 and A_0 modes also appeared in the ADRM configurations' detections shown in Figures 2(c) and 2(d). This could be verified much more clearly in the CWT results. A comparison between Figures 2(b), 2(c), and 2(d) revealed that the wave propagation in the fiber evidently resulted in an arrival time delay. The results also indicated that the change in arrival times was linear as shown in Figures 2(b), 2(c), and 2(d). Interestingly, the propagating wave components corresponding to the S_0 mode and the A_0 mode had the same velocity in the fiber. As a result, Figure 2 indicates that waveform detected using the PSFBG sensor in the ADRM configuration enable us to obtain accurate physical characteristics of the modes included in the wave propagating through the adhesive point.

Finite element method simulation was also carried out to valid the experimental results. From the simulation results, we clarified sensing characteristics of the ADRM configuration which was shown in the Figure 3.

Figure 3: Detection property of PS-FBG sensor in the ADRM configuration.

AE propagates in the structural plate as a Lamb wave, including the S_0 and A_0 modes, until its arrival at the adhesive point. However, when the Lamb wave was propagated from the plate to the fiber through the adhesive, it was transformed into the other type of wave, including longitudinal and transverse modes, which propagated in the optical fiber-ultrasonic waveguide. Then, the two modes continued to propagate along the optical fiber without any mode transformation due to a relatively ideal wave propagation system provided by the thin optical fiber with a small diameter (150 μm). The PS-FBG was produced in the core of the glass fiber; that is, the PS-FBG was in the neutral axis of a thin fiber. Also, the PS-FBG could only detect the axial strain, and therefore, only the longitudinal wave mode was detected. This implied that the detected wave components corresponding to the S_0 and A_0 modes propagated at the same velocity as that of the longitudinal wave. Hence, the S_0 mode or the A_0 mode in the detection results showed a linear delay change following the linearly changing distance between the PS-FBG sensor and the adhesive point. As a result, the PS-FBG sensor in the ADRM configuration demonstrated accurate remote sensing for the Lamb wave modes included in AE signals that propagated from the generation sources to the adhesive point.

3 DAMAGE TYPE IDENTIFICATION

As shown in Figure 4, A three-point bending test was implemented to generate damage in the $[90_2/0_2]_s$ coupon specimen ($L \times W \times H = 180 \times 20 \times 1.2 \text{ mm}^3$). A T700S/2500 (Toray Inc.) system was used in the fabrication of the laminate. Using the ADRM configuration, we glued the PS-FBG sensor on the plate to detect AEs generated during the bending test. The adhesive point was located 50 mm away from the loading pin. The distance between the PS-FBG and the adhesive point was 200 mm. Furthermore, as a reference to qualitatively verify that the S_0 and A_0 mode components were separated from the AE waves detected by the PS-FBG sensor, the two broad bandwidth PZT sensors were glued near the adhesive point but on two opposite surfaces [14].

Figure 4: Experimental setup of the three point bending test

The threshold of the channel connected with the PS-FBG sensor in the acquisition system was 75 dB, and the threshold of the channels connected with PZT sensors was 55 dB. These thresholds were high enough to eliminate the noise generated by friction between the loading pin and specimen. During post-processing, the AE signals were filtered over a frequency range from 150 kHz to 2 MHz to obtain the A_0 and S_0 modes clearly.

3.1 Waveform

First, after each AE event, the cross-sectional surface of the specimen was examined under a microscope to identify the corresponding damage.

We detected three types of AE signals and show their corresponding CWT results in the Figure 5 (a), (b) and (c). The analysis on the CWT results enabled us to identify the Lamb wave modes that were included in the received wave, clearly, in time-frequency field.

Figure 5: Continuous wavelet transformation (CWT) results for waves detected by the PS-FBG sensor in the ADRM configuration: AE generated by (a) transverse crack, (b) delamination and (c) fiber break.

After the AE events corresponding to the Figure 5 (a) and (b), transverse crack and delamination was, respectively, identified by observing the cross-sectional surface. From the two results, we qualitatively identified the S_0 and A_0 modes on the basis of dispersive characteristics [9]. The mode

separations were also validated using the PZT sensor-pair shown in the Figure 4. Then, the peak amplitude of the identified A_0 mode in Figure 5 (a) was found to be larger than that of the S_0 mode. To quantitatively evaluate this characteristic on AE wave, we calculated the ratio of the peak amplitude of the S_0 mode to that of the A_0 mode. This ratio was defined as the E/F ratio. In this research, the peak amplitudes were obtained from the CWT results. The E/F ratio obtained from Figure 5 (a) was 0.59.

In the Figure 5 (b), the separated wave mode components corresponding to the A_0 and S_0 modes also appeared in the AE signal corresponding to the event of delamination. The E/F ratio obtained from Figure 5 (b) was 1.35, which showed that the amplitude of S_0 was larger than that of A_0 in the AE generated by delamination.

Because of the broad bandwidth of the PS-FBG sensor, it was determined that not only the E/F ratio but also the peak frequency of AE was useful for identifying damage types in the CFRP laminates. The peak frequency corresponding to the AE of the transverse crack was 0.29 MHz, obtained from CWT results shown in Figure 5 (a). In contrast, the AE shown in Figure 5 (b) generated by the delamination had a higher peak frequency of 0.80 MHz.

The results also revealed that the peak frequency was directly related to the relative strength of A_0 and S_0 modes in the AEs, i.e., an AE had a lower peak frequency when the A_0 mode was stronger, and an AE had a higher peak frequency when the S_0 mode was stronger. This is because the A_0 mode dominated in the low frequency field of the AE wave, but the S_0 mode was present in the relatively high frequency field [9, 11]. For example, the A_0 mode was stronger than the S_0 mode in Figure 5 (a) and the peak frequency belongs to the A_0 mode in the AE generated by the transverse crack. In contrast, the peak frequency of the AE caused by delamination belongs to the stronger S_0 mode in Figure 5 (b).

Then, Figure 5 (c) shows one more type of AE detected using the PS-FBG sensor. We also found that the S_0 and A_0 modes appeared in the corresponding CWT result. However, the amplitude of the S_0 mode was much larger than that of the A_0 mode. The E/F ratio obtained from Figure 5 (c) was 6.2. Because of the strong S_0 mode, the AE signal shown in Figure 5 (c) had a maximum peak frequency of 0.89 MHz. Because of these characteristics, we believe that this AE was generated by another type of damage.

Previous research [9] has determined that the S_0 mode dominates in AEs caused by sources whose orientation is parallel to a plate surface and located close to the neutral plane in the thickness direction. Only damage in the 0-degree ply (0° -ply) of $[90_2/0_2]_s$ could possibly satisfy those conditions. Hence, we inferred that the AE shown in Figure 5 (c) was generated by a fiber break.

This section studied three types of AEs based on Lamb wave theory. The E/F ratio and the peak frequency obtained from CWT were helpful to quantitatively evaluate the characteristics of AE waves. The next section attempt to use both of the parameters simultaneously to develop a reliable damage identification method.

3.2 Damage Type Identification Based on E/F ratio and Peak Frequency

We conducted another three-point bending test for a specimen with the same $[90_2/0_2]_s$ laminate configuration. Thirty-four AE events were detected using the PS-FBG sensor in the ADRM configuration. E/F ratios and peak frequencies were calculated from CWT results of the AEs.

The E/F ratios and peak frequencies obtained from all of the AE events are shown in Figure 6 (a) and (b), respectively. However, both sets of results indicated that it was difficult to identify the three types of AE using a single parameter. Based on the analysis in section 3.1, we could identify that an AE with an E/F ratio of over 4.0 in Figure 6 (a) had been generated by fiber breakage. However, the differences between the other E/F ratios were too small to distinguish between AEs generated by a transverse crack or delamination. On the other hand, the peak frequencies in Figure 6 (b) separated into two groups. We identified the AEs with low peak frequencies as being generated by transverse cracks. However, it was still difficult to distinguish a fiber break from a delamination because of their similar peak frequency.

Hence, we utilized the two parameters, E/F ratio and peak frequency, simultaneously to build a new damage identification method. First, every AE event was expressed as a vector consisting of the peak

frequency and E/F ratio, which was plotted as one point in a 2-D space. Then, we applied a pattern recognition method—hierarchical clustering—that was based on the minimum distance between all of the points, to classify the AEs. As a result, three clusters of AE events corresponding to three types of damages were clearly determined in Figure 7. On the basis of the AE signal characteristics clarified in section 3.1, we identified the events in clusters 1, 2 and 3 as having been generated by fiber breaks, delaminations and transverse cracks, respectively.

Figure 6: Damage identification on the basis of a single physical parameter: (a) E/F ratios and (b) peak frequency.

Figure 7: Damage identification based on a pattern recognition method applied to AE events expressed by the EF ratios and the peak frequency.

From the classification result, we were able to obtain a quantitative damage identification standard in the laminates $[90_2/0_2]_S$ based on AE detection using a PS-FBG sensor in the ADRM configuration. When AE signals were filtered using a band filter from 150 kHz to 2 MHz, AE signals generated by transverse cracks had E/F ratios below 1, in the peak frequency range of 180 kHz to 390 kHz. The AE signals with E/F ratio from 1 to 3, corresponding to delamination events, had a peak frequency between 410 kHz and 900 kHz. The AEs caused by a fiber break had a distinctly large E/F ratio (over 4) in the peak frequency range of 750 kHz to 900 kHz.

Quantitative damage identification was made much clearer by combining the E/F ratio and peak frequency, in comparison with using only one of the two physical parameters. In particular, we used a pattern recognition method to classify the signals, so this method also has great potential for identifying damage among a large amount of AE events.

4 CONCLUSION

First, this research showed that ADRM configuration was able to detect AE wave correctly, because of the good waveguide system provided by the thin optical fiber and the sensitivity of the PS-FBG sensor to the axial strain in the core of the fiber. Then, using the remote measurement method, we achieved a stable AE detection under the three-point bending test, and clarified the characteristics of Lamb wave modes included in the AE signals. Moreover, quantitative physical parameters, i.e., E/F ratio and peak frequency was applied to evaluating the AEs quantitatively. The two AE parameters of E/F ratio and peak frequency enable us to apply a machine learning tool to the identification of damage types within a large number of AE signals. Hence, the new method proposed in this research could be used as an NDT method with great physical reliability for identifying and evaluating damage types in composites.

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